

ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL THINKING IN COMMUNICATIVE COMMUNICATION IN STUDENTS

Aripova Ulbosin

Assistant of the Tashkent State Technical University named after I. Karimov

Abstract. *This article discussed the importance of critical thinking in communicative communication in English. Evidence of this has been provided by many scholars.*

Keywords: *ESP, audio-language method, Harvey Siegel, Peter Fazione, Gnosology, TESOL, communicative language.*

The main purpose of training students who are studying in a non-philological direction is to provide them with a specific profession, to grow them as a necessary person for our society. To do this, in-depth teaching of a foreign language, English, the development of a communicative personality that can show its skills when it comes to the world scale, is the main goal that Foreign Language teachers set for themselves. After all, it is not a secret that personnel who can express their opinion in a foreign language in an independent way, logically and critically, can make their own outstanding contribution to the prosperity of our country.

Achieving such a result will also require the teacher to work equally from the student. First of all, it is desirable to have the necessary literature, unfortunately there is not exactly such literature for the effective organization of this process. While this is the case, ESP teachers are trying to use their pedagogical skills to achieve the intended goal. First of all, we need to find the answer to the question of what ESP is, which, when translated literally, is a process in which English is studied for special purposes. That is, any professional learns English only from those parties involved in his direction, for example, a doctor studies a chemical term and drugs, and a mechanic uses these terms in his communicative communication.

In Uzbekistan, English is studied as a foreign language, which is why we are called EFL learners. The main purpose of teaching students a second or foreign language is to ensure that they have the ability to successfully produce communication in a particular situation in which they are communicating in that language. In order

for communication to be successful, students must have the ability to think critically, only then will they become users, and not just effective language learners. In order to be successful in communicative communication, it is rare to know or translate only the grammar of a foreign language. In the last 10 years, special attention is paid to the communicative approach in the TESOL teaching system, requiring students to be critical in learning and using the language. Because when students express their feelings and thoughts in a foreign language, the lexical-grammar of that language, as well as the socio-cultural aspects of those who communicate in that language, should not be overlooked. Shifts in communicative language learning are mainly focused on the use of language in communication, and in this way the center is occupied by language learners rather than teachers. The main goal of applying this method is to make students able to communicate communicatively. By teaching communicative communication, students practice their thinking skills, which also take into account the audience and other factors during communication.

Many modern teaching techniques can be used in teaching communicative communication, such as natural approach, cooperative language learning, subject-based teaching, and task-based teaching. The communicative approach itself requires students to be more critical throughout the dialogue. The transition from the audio-language method to the communicative approach method in teaching a foreign language has ushered in a new era in the study of this language, as well as bringing elements of critical thinking into this area. Many foreign scientists have researched the use of a communicative approach,

and as proof of this, the following works can be cited as an example. Including "English as a medium of global communication "(Crystal 1997), the Humanist Movement in education (Nunan 1992)," sociology in traditional linguistics and integration of other disciplines" (Luke 2004). The globalization of the English language has also developed global trade and new communication technologies, resulting in many users of the same language ,with many English variants. An important factor is considered to be the need to be a critical language learner and applicator in order to be an effective interlocutor in this language.

Contemporary scholars have attempted to expand into the traditional definitions of critical thinking into quality, understanding, and process, adding concepts such as imagination, creativity ,excitement, exploration, knowledge linking ,empathy, feminist theory, for example. Some definitions of critical thinking exclude subjective experiences. The opinion of the eminent scholar Ennis was advanced and further studied by Harvey Siegel, Peter Fazione and Deanna Kuhn, according to whom " critical thinking is observation, experience, thinking that governs belief and action, learning is an intellectual and disciplined process of conceptualizing, applying, analyzing, synthesizing and evaluating, or gathering, generated data.

In simple words, critical thinking requires attention and brain activity from people. The use of pedagogical technologies aimed at the development of critical thinking increases the performance of students ' brain activity and helps to understand texts differently. That is, students can correctly summarize the issue with an objective attitude. It is no secret that the study of logical argumentation in turn is interconnected with critical thinking. That is, critical thinking is concerned with analyzing logical arguments and evaluating whether they are true or not. There is an area called gnoseology in which critical thinking emphasizes logical thinking, which necessarily makes it possible to distinguish between logical right and false conclusions. According to Loik's thought, in the first wave , The Thinker analyzes not from his own line of thought, but from connections between concepts and ideas.

Summing up, we can say that critical and logical thinking is an important process in the life of society. The thought process is a human-free ability that distinguishes a person from beings. With this ability, humanity has been developing and surviving on Earth for several thousand centuries. The thought process is essential not only for living, but also for living meaningfully.

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